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Chemical Investigation of the Leaves of *Breynia rhamnoids* Muell (Euphorbiaceae)

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BREYNIA rhamnoids Muell, commonly known as 'Surasaruni' grows throughout tropical India. Its different parts are indigenously used as local remedies for different diseases¹. The bark is astringent and its leaves are extensively used in the treatment of tonsils, uvula. No work seems to have been done on the leaves of this plant and hence a systematic study of this part was undertaken.

Dried and powdered leaves were thoroughly extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°). The concentrated extract was taken in ether and separated into acidic and neutral fractions.

Neutral fraction :

This was chromatographed over deactivated alumina whereupon the following compounds were obtained :

n-Alkanes : Elution of the column with petroleum ether afforded a crystalline product m.p. 52-60°. GLC analysis showed it to be a mixture of *n*-alkanes² (C₂₆ - C₃₄); *n*-triacontane (51.8%), *n*-dotriacontane (21.1%), *n*-nonacosane (8.3%), *n*-octacosane (6.0%), *n*-hentriacontane (5.3%), *n*-tri-triacontane (3.6%), and the minor quantities of *n*-hexacosane, *n*-heptacosane and *n*-tetratriacontane.

Aliphatic Alcohol : Further elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1, v/v) furnished ceryl alcohol³, m.p. 75°. It was identified on the basis of I.R., m.m.p. and by preparing its acetate, m.p. 60-62°.

Triterpenes : Elution of the column with benzene yielded a crystalline solid m.p. 137-139°, which responds to positive Liebermann Burchard test for triterpenes, GC-MS showed it to be a mixture of eight triterpenes. One of them, lanosterol⁴, m.p. 139-140° was separated and identified by m.m.p. determination, Co-TLC and Co-IR with an authentic specimen. Others are under process.

Phytosterol : Elution with benzene-chloroform (1 : 1, v/v) gave a white crystalline solid, m.p. 122-128°. GC-MS analysis of the substance (as trimethyl silyl ether derivative) showed it to be a mixture⁵ of cholesterol (0.4%) (M⁺ 458), campesterol (1.07%) (M⁺ 472), stigmasterol (4.82%) (M⁺ 484), β -sitosterol (92.55%) (M⁺ 486) and an unidentified substance mixed with sitosterol (1.07%), the two ion peaks 343, 386 are different from the β -sitosterol.

Acidic fraction :

The acidic fraction was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with ether-petroleum ether (1 : 9, v/v) gave a product, m.p. 65-69°. Its methyl ester melted at 59-62° and GLC analysis showed it to be a mixture of *n*-pentatriacontanoic (19.33%), *n*-triacontanoic (19.13%), *n*-tetracosanoic (17.23%), *n*-tricosanoic (15.75%), *n*-octacosanoic (3.24%), *n*-dotriacontanoic (3.21%), *n*-heptatriacontanoic (2.46%), *n*-hexacosanoic (2.00%), *n*-octatriacontanoic (1.80%) acids, along with the minor quantities of *n*-tetra-triacontanoic, *n*-cosanoic, *n*-pentacosanoic, *n*-heptacosanoic, *n*-hentriacontanoic, *n*-nonacosanoic, *n*-tri-triacontanoic and *n*-hexatriacontanoic acids.

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